

1 Selection of a Phase Change Material for Energy Storage by Multi- 2 Criteria Decision Method Regarding the Thermal Comfort in a 3 Vehicle

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10 **Abstract:** The use of vehicles is a daily matter worldwide, however, they remain parked most of
11 the time and commonly under the heating sun, leading to a rise in the internal temperature that
12 provokes heating discomfort, and when the temperature drops this discomfort to the user is felt
13 as cold. In this way, to reduce the distress drivers use air-conditioners in the first case and heaters
14 in the second event as needed, making the consumption of energy a common activity. This
15 research method takes a list of phase change materials used in some applications and makes a
16 novel selection of the best material to be implemented on a vehicle's rooftop, which is done by
17 Multicriteria Decision Methods means. The weighting is done by the new method based on the
18 removal effect of criteria (MERECE), the decision-making methods VIKOR, COPRAS and
19 TOPSIS choose the best material and the Spearman's correlation verify its agreement. The best
20 material selected unanimously is the savENRG PCM-HS22P, which latter was simulated by
21 finite elements methods, resulting in the reduction of 9°C in the internal air when heating and
22 conservation of 4°C in the cooling with a Phase Change Material layer of 20mm.

23 **Keywords:** Phase Change Material, Multicriteria Decision Method, MERECE, Finite Element Method.

24 1 Introduction

25 A problem that the population faces is that when a car is parked for minutes or
26 hours in un-shaded spaces under direct sunlight [1] or even on cloudy days [2], the
27 sunrays provokes a cabin to overheat [3] expressed as a raise of the internal temperature
28 of the air, this parameter is one of the measurable factors of discomfort in passengers,
29 and to avoid it the internal temperature should be in a range between 23°C to 28°C [4].
30 In this sense, the thermal comfort of the passenger in the automotive industry is an
31 important issue to take into consideration especially as a fuel economy improvement
32 opportunity [5]. In this way, the utilization of air conditioning can provide enough heat
33 in cold seasons and cooling in hot seasons to maintain a thermal balance on the users
34 [6]. However, the utilization of these systems can significantly impact fuel consumption
35 [7], and for low temperatures environment, studies have been developed to improve the
36 fuel efficiency in supplementary heating systems [8]. In this sense, this issue carries out
37 environmental problems like global warming from the greenhouse effect in the
38 atmosphere that can be managed by developing eco-friendly technologies, one of these
39 is Thermal Energy Storage (TES) which is the most efficient in using the available heat
40 resources. [9][10]. The TES can be found as active systems that need pumping work to
41 circulate a heat transfer fluid that is used for the charging and discharging process and
42 as passive systems that don't require any pumping [11]. The active systems have been
43 proved to be useful for cooling in phase-change thermal storing units [12], air ducts at
44 different flow configurations [13], and the passive system it's common to find in

45 thermal comfort textiles, thermal storage in buildings, electronics, coatings and
 46 automotive [11].

47

Nomenclature		COPRAS	Complex Proportional Assessment Methods
<i>Acronyms</i>		<i>Subscripts</i>	
TES	Thermal Energy Storage	η	number of materials
SHS	Sensible Heat Storage	m	number of criteria
LHS	Latent Heat Storage	Σ	Summation
PCM	Phase Change Material	W_j	Weighted values
MEREC	Method based on the Removal Effect of Criteria	X_{ij}	Values of the decision matrix
MCDM	Multi-criteria Decision Method	n_{ij}	Values of the MEREC normalized matrix
TOPSIS	Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution	r_{ij}	Values of the TOPSIS/COPRAS normalized matrix
VIKOR	Vlsekriterijumska Optimizacija I Kompromisno Resenje	V_{ij}	Values of the TOPSIS weighted matrix
		y_{ij}	Values of the COPRAS weighted matrix

1 In this sense, the TES can be classified into three types, Sensible Heat Storage
 2 (SHS), Latent Heat Storage (LHS), and Chemical Heat Storage [14]. In the case of
 3 LHS, the accumulation of heat takes place at a molecular level that leads to a phase
 4 transformation in the material [15]. Moreover, when talking about LHS the Phase
 5 Change Materials (PCMs) can be classified as organic, which are made of hydrocarbons
 6 and can be found in paraffin, fatty acids, and polyethylene glycol. The inorganic PCMs
 7 can be found as salts hydrates, molten salts, metals, and alloys, and finally, the eutectic
 8 mixtures are mixes of two or more composites that melt and solidify together [16].

9 On the other hand, in buildings, the effect of thermal energy storage aims to
 10 reduce the indoor temperatures and limits the internal air temperature to reach a
 11 maximum [17], where LHS has been used in walls, floors, and ceilings, showing an
 12 important impact on the temperature fluctuation by storing the solar energy [18]. In this
 13 sense, normally the heat storage comes from the sensible heat of the materials, making
 14 it have a low thermal energy storage capacity, however, the use of PCMs that use latent
 15 heat storage improves this capacity by the phase changing phenomena, producing an
 16 endothermic reaction when melting and an exothermic reaction when changing from
 17 liquid to solid by desorbing heat [19]. Even more, it is important to mention that the
 18 performance of the PCMs depends on variables like climate, orientation, and the
 19 amount of PCM [20], where it has been found that an optimal thickness can be found in

20 layers between 1mm and 20mm depending on the thermal conditions [21]. In this way,
21 in building applications, the increasing demand for thermal comfort also increases the
22 energy consumption [22], where, the PCMs has been useful in reducing the energy
23 consumption [20] and improving the energy efficiency of the air conditioning and
24 heating systems [23]

25 In the automotive industry, the PCMs have drawn attention to maintain the
26 thermal comfort in the cabin regarding the consumption and environmental problems
27 that come with the utilization of the air conditioning [24]. Moreover, another
28 application of the PCMs in vehicles is as a thermal stabilizer system for batteries of
29 electric and hybrid vehicles, where, the problem corresponds to the component's
30 overheat, resulting in permanent damage and even risk of explosion. In this way, the
31 PCM stores that overheat making it more efficient to reduce temperature than natural
32 convection or forced convection by a fan [10]. On the other hand, in the engine, there
33 have been researches with novel cooling systems, where the size of the radiator could be
34 reduced as well as the cooling fan system by minimizing the air drag force, where
35 another benefit is that the stored heat could help the cold ignite of the engine [25]. Even
36 more, there have been Organic Rankine Cycle latent heat recovery systems
37 implemented in engine tasks using PCMs [26], meaning that this technology has an
38 important automotive application. However, a challenge in the utilization of the PCMs
39 for the automotive industry is to use them the way it is used in buildings, where layers
40 of PCMs may store thermal energy insulating the internal environment during the day
41 and releasing that stored heat when the temperature starts to drop. In this sense, this
42 novel research aims to study this behavior since it has not been much explored.

43 Furthermore, taking into consideration the variety of PCMs and applications, the
44 PCMs can hold some options with quantitative selection criteria such as thermal
45 conductivity, latent heat of fusion, specific heat, density, and cost, among others [27]
46 [28]. In this sense, the selection can be managed with mathematical tools such as the
47 Multi-criteria Decision Methods (MCDM) that can perform an important role in the
48 decision analysis for small and large problems [29]. In this way, researchers have used
49 these methods in the selection of PCMs in several areas, like the Analytic Hierarchy
50 Process (AHP) to solve complex problems with multiple criteria, allowing to weight the
51 candidates and make a profit of it in solar energy storage applications [30], however,
52 this method has a subjective compound since the assessment of the criteria comes from
53 the experience and criterion of the decision-makers. In this sense, a novel method based
54 on the removal effects of criteria (MERECE) shows an interesting methodology to
55 determine the criteria weights on multicriteria decision-making problems [31].
56 Furthermore, the multicriteria optimization and compromise solution known as the
57 VIKOR method has been used successfully in the selection of PCMs for rooftop
58 insulation by considering the closeness with ideal solutions [32], taking into mind
59 characteristics such as conflicting and non-commensurable criteria [33]. On the other hand,
60 the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) has the
61 advantages of being easy to use with a simple number of steps that do not vary
62 regardless of the number of alternatives [34], also, it has been used for material
63 selection since this method considers the quantitative criteria for evaluation of
64 performance on qualitative criteria making an easier and accurate assessment, what has
65 been useful in the selection of PCMs for buildings [35], in this sense, the TOPSIS and

66 VIKOR methods have a similarity since both are based on the measure of distances
67 between the options [36]. Even more, the Complex Proportional Assessment Methods
68 (COPRAS) have accuracy and reliability acknowledged solving different engineering
69 problems [37] by assuming a direct and proportional degree of utility between criteria
70 that could be conflicting [38]. In this way, the MCDM had been used to sustain the best
71 choice of parameters before a simulation, like it was done before by choosing the
72 tradeoff factor and forming time to have the best friction distribution in superplastic
73 forming for vehicle's components with the TOPSIS method, therefore, the simulation
74 sustained the multicriteria selection [39]

75 In extension, the materials that are found as optimal have been simulated with
76 finite element analysis, this technique has been used in the automotive field in several
77 applications, like the design of disk brakes, where the software helped to conclude that
78 "geometric design of disc is an essential factor in its thermo-mechanical characteristic"
79 [40] allowing to know the thermal behavior of the system by computational means. In
80 this way, other researches showed that the PCMs had been simulated in thermal
81 applications for buildings applying 1D, 2D, and 3D mathematical models for the PCM's
82 capacity and enthalpy, where results were used for applications like office, single room,
83 and houses, displaying the performance, energy saving, comfort, etc. [41] of the
84 application. Moreover, in extensive research of the utilization of MDCM, these methods
85 have been used to select the best material to enhance a PCM by nanoparticles in a solar
86 storage application, the results showed that graphene was the best candidate followed by
87 aluminum and alumina, by these means, the nano-PCM was simulated allowing to
88 visualize the behavior of the best compound selected by Multi-criteria means [42].

89 In this way, even though there has been made research of MCDM with PCMs
90 and simulations, mostly it has aimed for the building industries but not in the
91 automotive comfort segment. In this sense, the objective of the present research is to
92 select and simulate the ideal PCM for TES in an automotive's rooftop application. In
93 this way, the selection is managed by MCDMs mean, taking as a principal reference
94 PCMs from bibliographical research that had been considered in some energy storage
95 applications. On the other hand, the simulation by computer-assisted engineering aims
96 to deliver the behavior of the best-selected PCM in the heating process and cooling
97 process in parking conditions, therefore, filling a not much-studied field with a novel
98 result. Furthermore, this research looks for a new technique to store energy from the sun
99 to give better comfort to the users of the automotive industry as it has been done for the
100 buildings sector, considering that a Multi-criteria selection evaluates different criteria
101 and chooses the best option with an objective perspective.

102 **2 Method and material**

103 Considering that the desirable characteristics of a PCM are phase change
104 temperature in a range between 23°C-28°C since this is the thermal comfort
105 temperature, also the properties needed are density, the heat of fusion, the specific heat,
106 and thermal conductivity (all in liquid state). In this sense, the selection starts with
107 bibliographical research with these considerations, where, 3 PCMs candidates came
108 from a list presented in a review for vehicle component thermal buffering by Jankowski
109 & McCluskey [43], 3 commercial salt hydrate PCMs presented by Kenisarin &
110 Mahkamov [44] for solar applications, and 14 PCMs presented by Rastogi et al. [45]

111 for air conditioning building applications. In this way, table 1 shows the PCMs and their
 112 thermal properties. Furthermore, each material has been assigned an “M” code only to
 113 refer it with this designation instead of the full name in the following process.

114 Moreover, the objective of this research is to use the PCMs proposed by the
 115 mentioned authors in different applications and take the best to an automotive rooftop
 116 application by MCDM means and simulate its thermal behavior under a parked
 117 condition on sunny days. Therefore, the main characteristics that the material must have
 118 are:

- 119 1. Phase Change between 23°C to 28°C
- 120 2. Good density for a low volume change when changing phases.
- 121 3. High fusion heat for an efficient phase change
- 122 4. High latent heat for efficient thermal storage
- 123 5. Good thermal conductivity to transmit the thermal energy.

124 In this sense, to satisfy the requirements expressed before, the thermal properties
 125 of table 1 fulfill the needs of the application, also, the criteria must be classified as
 126 beneficial and non-beneficial for the application of the MCDM. In this way, the
 127 beneficial criteria refer to those that have a higher numerical value makes them better
 128 and non-beneficial criteria act on the other way, the lower values make them better. The
 129 classification is determined as follows:

- 130 • Phase Change Temperature: Beneficial
- 131 • Density: Non-Beneficial
- 132 • The heat of fusion: Beneficial
- 133 • Specific heat capacity: Beneficial
- 134 • Thermal conductivity: Beneficial

135 Furthermore, table 1 holds the characteristics of the materials was used as
 136 decision matrix X , regarding n materials and m criteria for the MCDM in the following
 137 way:

$$138 \quad X \begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & X_{12} & \cdots & X_{1m} \\ X_{21} & X_{22} & \cdots & X_{2m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ X_{n1} & X_{n2} & \cdots & X_{nm} \end{bmatrix}$$

139 2.1 Method Based on the Removal Effect of Criteria

140 The candidate materials have been defined with the needed characteristics;
 141 however, the different criteria must be weighted. In this sense, the MEREC allows
 142 assigning greater weights to the criteria that have higher effects on the performance of
 143 the material [31]. The application of the method was done with the steps described by
 144 Keshavarz-Ghorabae et al., as follows:

- 145 1. Utilize the decision matrix defined before, where all the values should be
 146 greater than zero
- 147 2. The normalization of the matrix takes place considering the classification
 148 of beneficial and non-beneficial. In this sense, the minimum and
 149 maximum values for each criterion are found, these were used in
 150 equation 1 which defines the values for the beneficial criteria, and

151 equation 2 for the non-beneficial. These factors are integrated under the
 152 normalized matrix.

$$n_{ij} = \frac{\min_k X_{kj}}{X_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

153

$$n_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{\max_k X_{kj}} \quad (2)$$

154

3. The calculation of the overall performance (S_i) is made with equation 3
 155 by applying a logarithm measure based on a nonlinear function

$$S_i = \ln \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{m} \sum_j |\ln n_{ij}| \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

156

157

4. The performance of the alternatives by removing each criterion (S'_{ij}) is
 158 developed with equation 4. This step is similar to the previous stage with
 159 the difference that in the summation of the logarithms of the alternatives,
 160 a hole criterion is not considered, delivering different m values for every
 161 n alternative.

$$S'_{ij} = \ln \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k, k \neq j} |\ln n_{ik}| \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

162

163

5. The effect of removing a criterion (E_j) is calculated with the summation
 164 of absolute deviations using the following equation:

$$E_j = \sum_i |S'_{ij} - S_i| \quad (5)$$

165

166

6. The method concludes with the calculation of each criterion's objective
 167 weight using the removal effect as displayed in equation 6.
 168

$$w_j = \frac{E_j}{\sum_k E_k} \quad (6)$$

169

170

171 2.2 Method VIKOR

172

The VIKOR method solves selection problems by looking for a ranking where
 173 the alternative and criteria that will be used is the solution closest to the ideal [23]. In
 174 this way, since the candidate materials have been taken from building, automotive and
 175 solar applications, it is important to assess all of them for this novel application, in a
 176 way that the best material is the one that is closer to an almost perfect solution.

177

In this sense, the method is performed as expressed by Papathanasiou & Ploskas,
 178 that starts with the determination of the best (X_j^*) and the worst (X_j^-) values value of all
 179 criteria function, these values are related to the classification of beneficial non-
 180 beneficial criteria, for the case of the beneficial criteria $X_j^* = \max_i X_{ij}$ represents the
 181 maximum value among all the candidates and $X_j^- = \min_i X_{ij}$ is the minimum value among
 182 all which represents the worst. On The other hand, for the non-beneficial criteria it
 183 works oppositely, the best option is the one with the lowest value expressed as $X_j^* = \min_i$
 184 X_{ij} , and the worst alternative refers to the highest values meaning $X_j^- = \max_i X_{ij}$ [46].

185 Taking this consideration, a relationship between the weights of every criterion, the best
 186 and the worst values declared and the specific alternative is calculated, where two
 187 different rankings are developed, being the group of utility (S_i) the result of the
 188 summation of all the factors calculated for every material expressed in equation 7 and
 189 the group of regret (R_i) which is the maximum value obtained among all by using
 190 equation 8:

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n W_j \frac{X_j^* - X_{ij}}{X_j^* - X_j^-} \quad (7)$$

191

$$R_i = \max_j W_j \frac{X_j^* - X_{ij}}{X_j^* - X_j^-} \quad (8)$$

192 Furthermore, every material now has one factor S_i and R_i that represents them,
 193 where the maximum and minimum values among all are extracted and are represented as
 194 $S^* = \min_i S_i$; $S^- = \max_i S_i$ and $R^* = \min_i R_i$; $R^- = \max_i R_i$. On the other hand, the factor of
 195 “maximum utility” is calculated as $v = (n+1) \times (2n)^{-1}$ where n refers to the number of
 196 alternatives. In this way, these calculated factors are used in equation 9 to provide a
 197 third and the main ranking represented by the factor Q_i , where the best is the one closer
 198 to zero.

$$Q_i = v \times \frac{S_i - S^*}{S^- - S^*} + (1 - v) \times \frac{R_i - R^*}{R^- - R^*} \quad (9)$$

199 Moreover, following the methodology of Jahan & Edwards (2015), there must
 200 be done verification in the best-ranked option ($A^{(1)}$), where the conditions of acceptable
 201 advantage and acceptable stability must be fulfilled as follows:

- 202 • C1. Acceptable advantage:

$$QA^{(2)} - QA^{(1)} \geq DQ \quad (10)$$

203 Where:

204

$$DQ = \frac{1}{n - 1} \quad (11)$$

205 If this condition is not fulfilled, then a compromised solution is determined for
 206 the alternatives as follows:

$$QA^{(M)} - QA^{(1)} \leq DQ \quad (12)$$

207

- 208 • C2 Acceptable stability in decision-making.

209 In the secondary ranking of S_i and/or R_i the best alternative must be ($A^{(1)}$) if this
 210 condition of acceptable stability (C2) is the only one that has not been satisfied,
 211 then both ($A^{(1)}$) and ($A^{(2)}$) should be considered as a compromised solution.
 212

213 2.3 TOPSIS Method

214 The VIKOR method has the nature of proposing compromise solutions to
 215 decision-makers regarding the conflicting criteria [48], however, in this case, it is
 216 necessary to select only the best material, and to avoid this problem and give more

217 accuracy to the selection a second MCDM is considered which is the TOPSIS method.
 218 In this sense, from a finite number of alternatives, the TOPSIS method takes and
 219 classified them by similarity to the ideal solutions, looking for the alternatives to have
 220 the shortest distance to the ideal positive solution and the farthest from the negative
 221 [23]. In this way, the TOPSIS method that is similar to the VIKOR method differs in the
 222 fact that TOPSIS may agree that the best is the close to ideal but also it has a distance to
 223 the worst that can be considered as best.

224 In this sense, the development of TOPSIS is performed using the methodology
 225 of Opricovic & Tzeng, starting with the utilization of the decision matrix to calculate
 226 the normalized matrix expressed with equation 13.

$$r_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n X_{ij}^2}} \quad (13)$$

227 The method continues with the calculation of the weighted matrix, in this case,
 228 every factor of the normalized matrix is multiplied by the weight that has been assigned
 229 by the MERC, delivering a specific attribute to the matrix as expressed by equation 14.

$$V_{ij} = r_{ij} * W_j \quad (14)$$

230

231 In this sense, the weighted matrix displays a set of values where the ideal
 232 positive solutions (V^+) and anti-ideal negative solutions (V^-) for each criterion can be
 233 found. These are determinately taking into consideration the classification of beneficial
 234 and non-beneficial criteria, and similarly as performed in the method VIKOR for the
 235 beneficial criteria the maximum value $V^+ = \max_j V_{ij}$ is the positive solution, the minimum
 236 $V^- = \min_j V_{ij}$ represents the negative solution, and likewise for the non-beneficial criteria
 237 works on the other way, with the minimum value $V^+ = \min_j V_{ij}$ as the positive solution and
 238 the maximum $V^- = \max_j V_{ij}$ for the negative solution.

239 In this way, with the knowledge where the solutions are framed, the method
 240 requires to calculate the distances of every alternative with equation 15 that measures
 241 the separation of the weighted factor to the positive solution (D_j^*) and in the same way,
 242 equation 16 calculate the distance to the negative solution (D_j^-) as follows.

$$D_j^* = (\sum_{j=1}^m (V_{ij} - V^+)^2)^{0.5} \quad (15)$$

243

$$D_j^- = (\sum_{j=1}^m (V_{ij} - V^-)^2)^{0.5} \quad (16)$$

244

245 Furthermore, now that every candidate material has a determinate distance to the
 246 positive and negative solutions, it is possible to calculate the closeness to the ideal
 247 solution (C_i) by applying equation 17, where the results are comprehended between a
 248 value of 0 and 1 and the best candidate material is the one closer to 1.

$$C_j = \frac{D_j^-}{D_j^* + D_j^-} \quad (17)$$

249 **2.4 COPRAS Method**

250 The COPRAS method evaluates different options and ranks the alternatives
 251 considering the utility degree or significance of it by using grey numbers, these numbers
 252 come from the grey theory for insufficient or incomplete information [23]. In this sense,
 253 the COPRAS method gives a third perspective of the material selection that is focused
 254 on the utility of the candidate rather than the ideal or non-ideal solutions that have been
 255 explored before, making it a good option to compare the results that have been proposed
 256 before.

257 The application of the method is performed as expressed in the research done by
 258 Mousavi-Nasab & Sotoudeh-Anvari [50], who starts with the development of
 259 normalization of the decision matrix using equation 18, in this case, it is similar to the
 260 TOPSIS method but COPRAS divided the factors of the decision matrix for the
 261 summation of this values on every criterion making it simpler. However, the following
 262 step is also like in the previous method, where the normalized matrix multiplies its
 263 values dot the weight calculated at the start of the selection using equation 19.

$$r_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m X_{ij}} \quad (18)$$

264

$$y_{ij} = r_{ij} * W_j \quad (19)$$

265

266 In this way, the weighted normalized scores that have been found are separated
 267 depending on the classification of beneficial (y_{+ij}) and non-beneficial criteria (y_{-ij}),
 268 allowing to calculate the summation of the beneficial criteria (S_{+i}) with equation 20, and
 269 in the same way for the non-beneficial criteria (S_{-i}) with equation 21. The calculation of
 270 these factors allows us to correlate them to calculate the non-percentage value of the
 271 comparative significance COPRAS (Q_i) with equation 22.

$$S_{+i} = \sum_{j=1}^n y_{+ij} \quad (20)$$

272

$$S_{-i} = \sum_{j=1}^n y_{-ij} \quad (21)$$

273

274

$$Q_i = S_{+i} + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m S_{-i}}{S_{-i} \sum_{i=1}^m (S_{-i})^{-1}} \quad (22)$$

275

276 In this way, Q_{max} is the maximum Q_i and the values obtained for every
 277 candidate material allows to determinate the level of utility (U_i) of every option in a

278 percentual manner by using equation 23, where the nearest to 100% is the most useful
279 and hence the best

$$U_i = \left(\frac{Q_i}{Q_{max}} \right) * 100\% \quad (23)$$

280 2.5 Spearman's correlation coefficient

281 The MCDM may deliver a different result of which material is the best, in this
282 sense, they all lever up to choose the material that will have the best performance on the
283 application. In this way, the chosen MCDM are compared to each other regarding the
284 level of agreement that they have with each other.

285 Since we have various sets of results due to the different methods, we look for a
286 technique that allows us to measure the relation that keeps between this nonlinear data,
287 for this, the spearman's correlation coefficient quantifies the strength between the
288 variables, if there is not any duplicated data, the perfect correlation of +1 or -1 appears
289 for the perfect monotone function of the other, and if 0 then it is described as not
290 associated [23], this is calculated with the following equation described by Zar, where
291 the correlations are done comparing the ranking results of every method to each other in
292 this way: VIKOR-TOPSIS; VIKOR-COPRAS and TOPSIS-COPRAS. In this way,
293 following equation 24, d_i represents the rank difference of a material in the different
294 MCDM. Since these subtractions are elevated to a square index, the inverted
295 comparisons will be the same.

$$Rs = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2}{(n^3 - n)} \quad (24)$$

296

297 2.6 Simulation

298 The material has been selected and for the simulation, the PCM was created with
299 the properties of the winner material, which is required to introduce density, thermal
300 conductivity, and specific heat for the thermal analysis. In this way, the next step
301 consists in the generation of the geometry of a vehicle to be simulated by computational
302 means, where the definition of the material selected to act as the roof was made by
303 using the Software CES-Granta Edupack. In this sense, the software holds an important
304 library of materials, the selection begins by choosing the library "Advance Level 3"
305 which holds a database of 4026 materials. In this way, the search option of the software
306 allows to use of a search engine and filter the materials by keywords, where
307 "Automotive"; "Roof", and "Steel" were introduced delivering three concrete materials.
308 The Press hardening steel 22MnB5 coated and uncoated materials referees as roof
309 reinforcement which is not the needed application, leaving the steel Bake hardening
310 YS260 cold rolled, which is described as used for automotive applications, where the
311 roofs are one of its typical use [52]. Figure 1 shows the CAD model that will be
312 simulated using finite element methods that solve differential equations, where the
313 conduction of energy follows Fourier's law [53] and newton's law of cooling state for
314 convection [54]. In this case, the air is modeled as a solid since the study considers that
315 there is no airflow, and the PCM remains as a solid that allows calculating the
316 temperature and heat flow based on the heat sources and thermal transfer [55] on a static
317 internal environment of the vehicle. The simulation took two events, the first when the

318 roof is heating up and the PCM is storing energy, and the second where the roof is
 319 cooling down and the PCM releases the stored energy.

Figure 1. CAD Model

320
 321

2.7 Boundary conditions

322 According to Dadour et al. [56], the temperature that a parked car for two weeks
 323 with a black rooftop that reflects the minimum sunlight radiations can reach is near
 324 45°C in 15 hours of daytime starting at a temperature of 20°C, however, there is a peak
 325 of cooling and the temperature reduces to 12°C in 10 hours. In this sense, the conditions
 326 will be taken from here to the maximum temperature in 5 hours [56]

328 Moreover, a condition of convection will be used only for the heat release from
 329 the PCM to the internal air of the vehicle. In this sense, since the convection coefficient
 330 for free gases is found in the range of $2 \frac{W}{m^2K}$ and $25 \frac{W}{m^2K}$ [57], there was used a middle
 331 value of $12 \frac{W}{m^2K}$. On the other hand, to compare the influence of the PCM a comparison
 332 was performed first without the PCM, then with the PCM with a thickness of 5mm,
 333 10mm, and 20mm. The boundary conditions of this event are described in table 2.

334 Furthermore, for the second event where the temperature drops, the same
 335 research of Dadour et al. [56] expresses that after reaching the maximum temperature
 336 the cooling starts until dropping to 12 °C in 15 hours. However, the initial conditions of
 337 this event are the final conditions of the simulation with a PCM of 20mm of thickness.
 338 Since this system store more energy, the boundary conditions of this event is displayed
 339 in table 3. On the other hand, these heat conditions on the rooftop are replicated on the
 340 software with the slopes presented in figure 2 a) for the first event, figure 2 b) for the
 341 second event, and only considers the heat that the roof manages, not the radiation of the
 342 sun as a variable.

343

Figure 2. Roof's temperature conditions.

344

345 In this sense, the CAD model has no important complications, but the transient
346 state simulation needed a reliable mesh, hence the configurations to fulfill these
347 requirements are displayed in table 4 for the 20 mm PCM models that represent the
348 most complex. Even more, it's important to outline that in the advanced options of the
349 thermal simulation properties, it was determined that the results must have a
350 convergence tolerance of 0.1% solved by the software.

351 **3 Results and discussion**

352

353 **3.1 Weighted method**

354 The method based on the removal effect of the criteria calculated an objective
355 weight for every criterion displayed in table 5, in this way, it is showing the calculations
356 for the appraisal scores of the deviation presented in the removal of each criterion, the
357 consequences effect, and the weight derived from it. In this sense, the methods showed
358 that the specific heat capacity has more significant importance since this property is
359 responsible of store the energy to isolate the heat and release it when necessary. In this
360 way, other researchers like Rathod & Kanzaria [29] gives more importance to the latent
361 heat of PCMs, however, since the method used was the AHP, which is a subjective
362 method, the author's remarks that this weight can be different depending on the user and
363 application [29]. In this sense, the MEREC showed an objective weight that displays a
364 different result but is very acceptable for our application since the importance of the
365 criteria is determined by focusing on the exclusion perspective rather than the inclusion
366 [58].

367 **3.2 Results of VIKOR**

368 The calculation of the VIKOR method along with the different rankings S_i , R_i ,
369 and Q_i are displayed in table 6. The main ranking shows that the best materials are the
370 ones with index Q nearest to 0, where the material M8 corresponding to the savENRG
371 PCM-HS22P stands as the best. This material is an organic PCM that is used in the
372 storage of great energy, has low cost, specific composition, and is very pure according
373 to the manufacturer.

374 Furthermore, for confirmation of the acceptable advantage (C1) of the best
375 material for the 20 compounds the value $DQ = 0.052$, in this sense, it can be seen that
376 the advantage is accomplished since the de distance of the second to the first is 0.12
377 which is greater than DQ . On the other hand, the analysis of the acceptable stability
378 (C2) showed that the best material is not the best for the ranking R_i , however, it has the
379 value nearest to zero with 0.31 on the S_i ranking, delivering that it also fulfills the
380 acceptable stability condition in the decision making. Moreover, even previously it has
381 been concluded that VIKOR is the best methodology for the selection of materials in
382 automotive applications since this delivers a compromise set of solutions as result [33],
383 in this case, it was not necessary.

384 **3.3 TOPSIS Method**

385 The results of the TOPSIS method are displayed in table 7, where it can be seen
386 the weighted matrix that comes from the normalization multiplies for the weight of each
387 criterion, at the bottom, it is expressed the values corresponding to the best and the
388 worst depending on the beneficial and non-beneficial classification of the criteria.
389 Furthermore, the table shows the distances to these positive and negative solutions
390 followed by the calculation of the closeness to the ideal solution that is used to rank the
391 materials.

392 The TOPSIS method shows that again the M8 material that belongs to the
393 savENRG PCM-HS22P is the optimum material. Moreover, this method has
394 successfully selected PCMs for thermal management of electronic devices, with results
395 that are congruent to experimental research. In this sense, it was concluded that the
396 TOPSIS method along with a weighted method plays a crucial role to narrow down a
397 possible selection of a wrong PCM [34]

398 **3.4 COPRAS Method**

399 The results of the COPRAS method are shown in table 8, where the normalized matrix
400 has been multiplied by the corresponding weight delivering the factors that are used to
401 calculate the normalized weighted scores that are extracted from the summation of the
402 beneficial and non-beneficial criteria. Furthermore, it is shown the significance of the
403 option and the utility of every material, making it possible to rank the alternatives closer
404 to 100% as the best. The results show that the material M8 savENRG PCM-HS22P
405 again is the best material. In this sense, this method in engineering fields has shown to
406 be useful since it enables the decision-maker to determine the overall efficiency of the
407 different options [38], a characteristic that allowed us to establish the most useful
408 material among 20 candidates.

409 **3.5 Spearman's correlation results**

410 Lastly, Table 9 shows the results of the spearman's correlation where all of them
411 are higher than 0.9 which not only indicates an excellent positive correlation between
412 them, but their correlation is near to 1 making it almost perfect. It's important to
413 mention that this correlation shows a consistency in the results, studies where the same
414 data evaluated for TOPIS and VIKOR have thrown a negative spearman's coefficient,
415 reflecting that in that case there isn't congruence in the results [36]. In this research, the
416 correlation shows that is not perfect but has a correlation on the best materials that is the
417 objective. Moreover, taking into consideration that the material savENRG PCM-HS22P
418 was chosen as the best in the 3 methods, this is the one considered as the chosen for the
419 simulation, table 10 displays the properties of this material.

420 It's important to point out that this research has different applications as what
421 Rastogi et al.[45] had done, they prioritized the Figures of Merit where the extraction
422 of heat plays the most important part of the job, in our case different criteria had been
423 taken into account since the application demands for a specific phase change
424 temperature range, heat storage, and release. On the other hand, the work of Beltrán &
425 Martínez-Gómez[23], showed that in an MCDM there could be an agreement of two out
426 of three methods and also have a correlation not as good as developed by our research,
427 however, in the application the material performs as the best expected, giving the
428 security that the chosen material by MCDM is the best. Moreover, the research of

429 Socaciu et al.[24] made a selection of a PCM for thermal comfort in automotive by
430 MCDM, where the best materials for the application were the SavEnrg PCM-Hs01P,
431 SavEnrg PCM-Hs29P, and SavEnrg PCM-Hs22P [24]. In this sense, it can be seen that
432 all the materials come from the same house as our best two PCMs, meaning that our
433 selection that took a different method corroborates that this material is the best among
434 the chosen universe for this research and that the selection is appropriate.

435 **3.6 Simulation Results.**

436 This research has selected and simulated a PCM that enhances the balance of
437 heat exchange of the passenger and the environment, trying to reduce the breach
438 between the internal air and the body heat to maintain an optimal core temperature,
439 leading to thermal comfort for the user [6]. The results of the temperature at every hour
440 in the internal temperature and the maximum temperature are displayed in table 11, and
441 these results are discussed as follows.

442 The behavior of the PCM as a thermal storage system was simulated with the
443 before-mentioned parameters. In this sense, it shows that the temperature of internal air
444 increases with the rise of the temperature on the rooftop. Moreover, figure 2 a) shows
445 how the internal air is practically the same as the rooftop. On the other hand, figure 2 b)
446 shows how the vehicle with the PCM with a layer of 20mm isolates the raise of the
447 temperature on the internal air. In this way, table 11 displays the values for the
448 maximum temperature and the temperature of the internal air in every step of the
449 simulation, where it can be seen how the temperature of the internal air is reduced by
450 near 9°C.

a)

b)

451

452

Figure 3. Charging simulation comparison

453

454

455

456

457

458

459

On the other hand, different researches with different PCMs reported similar temperature reduction, where a PCM made of 1-dodecanol reduced the temperature in 10°C [1], coconut oil reached 17°C [3], RT-27 managed nearly 5°C in the passenger's temperature and 10°C for the steering wheel [2]. These results with different kinds of PCMs show that our results are congruent with experimental data. Furthermore, the results of the temperature in the simulation with a PCM with a thickness of 5mm and 10 mm can be found in figures 3 and 4.

460
 461

Figure 4. PCM 5mm

462
 463

Figure 5. PCM 10mm

464 The storing of the energy from the PCM is responsible to avoid the heating of
 465 the internal air, this phenomenon can be seen in figure 6, where at the top of the PCM
 466 there is a heat flux but at the bottom this is reduced, meaning that part of the thermal
 467 energy gets stored in the PCM and is not released to the internal air. In a comparison
 468 made in buildings with a PCM, brickbat, and sand, it was concluded that the high
 469 specific heat of the PCM allows preventing the heat transfer from outdoor to the internal
 470 air, phenomena that were proven by comparing the reduction in the peak of heat flux
 471 [22] and can be seen in this application.

472
473

Figure 6. Heat Flux in PCM

474 Furthermore, for comparative interest the simulation study was made also with
 475 the worst-ranked PCM which is the EPS – E23, even that in terms of temperature there
 476 was not registered an important difference, the study of temperature gradient on the
 477 inferior edge of the PCM allowed to compare both materials, showing that in average
 478 the temperature of the SavEnergy PCM-HS22P is lower for every cm of material
 479 compared with the EPS-E23, where a decreasing temperature gradient means a
 480 decreased temperature difference that improves the temperature uniformity [59], this
 481 could mean that the best material presents a better thermal stability and energy
 482 conservation allowing to maintain a stable temperature. The curves for these studies are
 483 displayed in figure 7 a) for the SavEnergy PCM-HS2P and 7 b) for EPS-E23

484

Figure 7. Temperature gradient

485 The discharging event, on the other hand, aims for the PCM to maintain a warm
 486 temperature while this drop. In this sense, figure 6 shows how while the rooftop has a
 487 temperature that fell from 45°C to 12°C the temperature of the internal air fell from
 488 37°C to 16°C. In this way, the PCM released its thermal energy stored in the internal air,
 489 making it more comfortable over time.

Figure 8. Discharge

490
491

492 Moreover, the research on the discharging event has taken place in building
 493 applications and not much as in automotive, this researches done in the building sector
 494 has shown the same phenomena where reaching the heat flux peak was delayed by the
 495 utilization of the PCM [21] and also, concluding that the effectiveness of isolation of a
 496 PCM is better than an ordinary wall [20]. In this sense, it was demonstrated in a
 497 discharging process of a building wall that the regular wall losses more energy without
 498 a PCM, meaning that the PCMs system is suitable for cooling [20]. The phenomenon of
 499 PCMs in discharging is explained where the material starts to freeze and release heat as
 500 latent energy, in the range of the temperature that holds the solid and liquid state, where
 501 the melting process takes double of time since the buoyancy is an important factor to
 502 take in consideration during the discharging process [14]. This behavior shown in
 503 buildings has a similarity with our research, contributing that the PCMs not only have
 504 the isolation property but also can store energy that can be useful when the sun is no
 505 longer available and the environment gets cold, improving the thermal comfort in this
 506 event.

507 However, even though the results of the comparison between charging with and
 508 without PCM, and the discharging event shown a clear behavior of the system, it's
 509 important to mention that this scenario only simulates an empty room, it has been
 510 established that simulation of rooms in buildings are affected by internal heat load, and
 511 optimization can be done when occupation scenarios are taking into account [17].

512 4 Conclusions

513 Considering a list of PCMs that has been studied for thermal comfort in
 514 buildings, solar energy storage, and automotive applications, these candidates were
 515 chosen for thermal comfort in vehicles for its phase change temperature that matches
 516 the thermal comfort range. In this sense, among all the best materials was selected
 517 MCDM. This PCM is the savENRG PCM-HS22P and is shown to have the best
 518 properties for heat storage application in an automotive industry among 20 other
 519 materials, resulting in the ideal for a vehicle's rooftop application.

520 The MEREC weighted the criteria as an objective method based on the removal
 521 effect of a criterion, leading to an acceptable result on the MCDM. The MEREC proved
 522 to be reliable and as a novel method deserves to be used for decision-making problems.

523 The MCDM used were VIKOR, COPRAS, and TOPSIS, these methods
524 evaluated the 20 materials and ranked them in order from the best to the worst. When
525 using various MCDM sometimes occurs that each method has the best material,
526 however, in this research the three methods had the savENRG PCM-HS22P as the best
527 result. Furthermore, the correlation between these results was verified by Spearman's
528 relation, resulting in a reliable selection, assuring that this material is apt to the task.

529 The simulation showed that the selected material as a PCM can improve the
530 thermal comfort of the vehicle. In this sense, showing that without the PCM the internal
531 air reached almost as the high environment temperature, however, when introducing the
532 PCM it showed to lower this temperature, where a layer of 20mm of PCM allowed to
533 diminish the temperature by almost 9°C.

534 The simulation of the discharging event also showed that the PCM allows to
535 maintaining a better temperature inside the cabin by making differentiation of 4°C
536 warmer in comparison to the simulated temperature of the outside, giving a better
537 comfort for the passenger's when the temperature drops.

538 It is demonstrated by computation means that the use of a PCM of savENRG
539 PCM-HS22P with a layer of 20mm can improve the thermal comfort in the vehicle,
540 reducing the need of using the heater or the air conditioner.

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547 **5 References**

- 548 [1] M. Purusothaman, K. Saichand, C. Sam Cornilius, and R. Siva, "Experimental
549 Investigation of Thermal Performance in a Vehicle Cabin Test Setup With Pcm
550 in the Roof Experimental Investigation of Thermal Performance in a Vehicle
551 Cabin Test Setup With Pcm in the Roof," 2017, doi: 10.1088/1757-
552 899X/197/1/012073.
- 553 [2] E. Oró, E. de Jong, and L. F. Cabeza, "Experimental analysis of a car
554 incorporating phase change material," *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 7, pp. 131–135,
555 Aug. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2016.05.003.
- 556 [3] C. A. Saleel, M. A. Mujeebu, and S. Algarni, "Coconut oil as phase change
557 material to maintain thermal comfort in passenger vehicles," *J. Therm. Anal.*
558 *Calorim.*, vol. 136, no. 2, pp. 629–636, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10973-018-7676-y.
- 559 [4] M. Simion, L. Socaciu, and P. Unguresan, "Factors which Influence the Thermal
560 Comfort Inside of Vehicles," in *Energy Procedia*, Jan. 2016, vol. 85, pp. 472–
561 480, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2015.12.229.
- 562 [5] B. H. Kang and H. J. Lee, "A Review of Recent Research on Automotive HVAC
563 Systems for EVs," *Int. J. Air-Conditioning Refrig.*, vol. 25, no. 04, p. 1730003,
564 2017, doi: 10.1142/S2010132517300038.

- 565 [6] I. Holmer, H. Nilsson, M. Bohm, and O. Noren, "Thermal Aspects of Vehicle
566 Comfort," *Appl. Hum. Sci.*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 159–165, 1995, doi:
567 10.2114/ahs.14.159.
- 568 [7] R. Farrington and J. Rugh, "Impact of Vehicle Air-Conditioning on Fuel
569 Economy, Tailpipe Emissions, and Electric Vehicle Range: Preprint," 2000,
570 [Online]. Available: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/764573>.
- 571 [8] D. Antonijevic and R. Heckt, "Heat pump supplemental heating system for motor
572 vehicles," *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part D J. Automob. Eng.*, vol. 218, no. 10, pp.
573 1111–1115, 2004, doi: 10.1177/095440700421801005.
- 574 [9] D. G. Prajapati and B. Kandasubramanian, "Biodegradable Polymeric Solid
575 Framework-Based Organic Phase-Change Materials for Thermal Energy
576 Storage," *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 58, pp. 10652–10677, 2019, doi:
577 10.1021/acs.iecr.9b01693.
- 578 [10] J. Jagemont, N. Omar, P. Van den Bossche, and J. Mierlo, "Phase-change
579 materials (PCM) for automotive applications: A review," *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, vol.
580 132, pp. 308–320, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.12.097.
- 581 [11] G. Alva, Y. Lin, and G. Fang, "An overview of thermal energy storage systems,"
582 *Energy*, vol. 144. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 341–378, Feb. 01, 2018, doi:
583 10.1016/j.energy.2017.12.037.
- 584 [12] S. Farah, M. Liu, and W. Saman, "Numerical investigation of phase change
585 material thermal storage for space cooling," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 239, pp. 526–535,
586 Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.01.197.
- 587 [13] M. Iten and S. Liu, "Experimental Study on the Performance of RT 25 to be Used
588 as Ambient Energy Storage," in *Energy Procedia*, May 2015, vol. 70, pp. 229–
589 240, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2015.02.119.
- 590 [14] A. Alhusseney, N. Al-Zurfi, A. Nasser, A. Al-Fatlawi, and M. Aljanabi, "Impact
591 of using a PCM-metal foam composite on charging/discharging process of
592 bundled-tube LHTES units," *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.*, vol. 150, p. 119320, Apr.
593 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2020.119320.
- 594 [15] H. Nazir *et al.*, "Recent developments in phase change materials for energy
595 storage applications: A review," *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.*, vol. 129, pp. 491–523,
596 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2018.09.126.
- 597 [16] N. Zhang, Y. Yuan, X. Cao, Y. Du, Z. Zhang, and Y. Gui, "Latent Heat Thermal
598 Energy Storage Systems with Solid–Liquid Phase Change Materials: A Review,"
599 *Adv. Eng. Mater.*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 1–30, 2018, doi: 10.1002/adem.201700753.
- 600 [17] F. Kuznik, D. David, K. Johannes, and J. J. Roux, "A review on phase change
601 materials integrated in building walls," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy
602 Reviews*, vol. 15, no. 1. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 379–391, Jan. 01, 2011, doi:
603 10.1016/j.rser.2010.08.019.
- 604 [18] D. Zhou, C. Y. Zhao, and Y. Tian, "Review on thermal energy storage with phase
605 change materials (PCMs) in building applications," *Applied Energy*, vol. 92.
606 Elsevier Ltd, pp. 593–605, Apr. 01, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2011.08.025.
- 607 [19] F. Kuznik and J. Virgone, "Experimental assessment of a phase change material

- 608 for wall building use,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 86, no. 10, pp. 2038–2046, Oct. 2009,
609 doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2009.01.004.
- 610 [20] H. Liu and H. B. Awbi, “Performance of phase change material boards under
611 natural convection,” *Build. Environ.*, vol. 44, no. 9, pp. 1788–1793, Sep. 2009,
612 doi: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2008.12.002.
- 613 [21] M. Arıcı, F. Bilgin, S. Nižetić, and H. Karabay, “PCM integrated to external
614 building walls: An optimization study on maximum activation of latent heat,”
615 *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, vol. 165, p. 114560, Jan. 2020, doi:
616 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2019.114560.
- 617 [22] R. J. Khan, M. Z. H. Bhuiyan, and D. H. Ahmed, “Investigation of heat transfer
618 of a building wall in the presence of phase change material (PCM),” *Energy Built
619 Environ.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 199–206, Apr. 2020, doi:
620 10.1016/j.enbenv.2020.01.002.
- 621 [23] R. D. Beltrán and J. Martínez-Gómez, “Analysis of phase change materials
622 (PCM) for building wallboards based on the effect of environment,” *J. Build.
623 Eng.*, vol. 24, no. February, p. 100726, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jobe.2019.02.018.
- 624 [24] L. Socaciu, O. Giurgiu, D. Banyai, and M. Simion, “PCM selection using AHP
625 method to maintain thermal comfort of the vehicle occupants,” in *Energy
626 Procedia*, Jan. 2016, vol. 85, pp. 489–497, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2015.12.232.
- 627 [25] K. Kim, K. Choi, Y. Kim, K. Lee, and K. Lee, “Feasibility study on a novel
628 cooling technique using a phase change material in an automotive engine,”
629 *Energy*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 478–484, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2009.10.015.
- 630 [26] X. Yu, Z. Li, Y. Lu, R. Huang, and A. P. Roskilly, “Investigation of organic
631 Rankine cycle integrated with double latent thermal energy storage for engine
632 waste heat recovery,” *Energy*, vol. 170, pp. 1098–1112, Mar. 2019, doi:
633 10.1016/j.energy.2018.12.196.
- 634 [27] K. Yang, N. Zhu, C. Chang, D. Wang, S. Yang, and S. Ma, “A methodological
635 concept for phase change material selection based on multi-criteria decision
636 making (MCDM): A case study,” *Energy*, vol. 165, pp. 1085–1096, Dec. 2018,
637 doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2018.10.022.
- 638 [28] A. Nadeem, K. Rakhman, and M. A. Hossain, “PHASE CHANGE MATERIALS
639 RANKING BY USING THE ANALYTIC HIERARCHY PROCESS.,” *Proc.
640 Int. Struct. Eng. Constr.*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. CPM-09-1 to CPM-09-6, 2020, doi:
641 [https://doi.org/10.14455/isec.res.2020.7\(1\).cpm-09](https://doi.org/10.14455/isec.res.2020.7(1).cpm-09).
- 642 [29] M. K. Rathod and H. V. Kanzaria, “A methodological concept for phase change
643 material selection based on multiple criteria decision analysis with and without
644 fuzzy environment,” *Mater. Des.*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 3578–3585, Jun. 2011, doi:
645 10.1016/j.matdes.2011.02.040.
- 646 [30] A. E. Amer, K. Rahmani, and V. A. Lebedev, “Using the Analytic Hierarchy
647 Process ({AHP}) method for selection of phase change materials for solar energy
648 storage applications,” *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.*, vol. 1614, p. 12022, 2020, doi:
649 10.1088/1742-6596/1614/1/012022.
- 650 [31] M. Keshavarz-Ghorabae, M. Amiri, E. K. Zavadskas, Z. Turskis, and J.

- 651 Antucheviciene, “Determination of Objective Weights Using a New Method
652 Based on the Removal Effects of Criteria (MERECE),” *Symmetry (Basel)*., vol. 13,
653 no. 4, 2021, doi: 10.3390/sym13040525.
- 654 [32] A. Méndez, J. Martínez-Gómez, F. Rodríguez, and J. F. Nicolalde, “Selección de
655 un material de cambio de fase mediante el uso del método de selección
656 multicriterio para su uso en un sistema de almacenamiento térmico automotriz,”
657 in *RISTI - Revista Iberica de Sistemas e Tecnologias de Informacao*, no. E32,
658 2020, pp. 113–125.
- 659 [33] R. Jeya Girubha and S. Vinodh, “Application of fuzzy VIKOR and
660 environmental impact analysis for material selection of an automotive
661 component,” *Mater. Des.*, vol. 37, pp. 478–486, May 2012, doi:
662 10.1016/j.matdes.2012.01.022.
- 663 [34] A. Kumar, R. Kothari, S. K. Sahu, and S. I. Kundalwal, “Selection of phase-
664 change material for thermal management of electronic devices using multi-
665 attribute decision-making technique,” *Int. J. Energy Res.*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp.
666 2023–2042, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.5896>.
- 667 [35] T. Mukhamet, S. Kobeyev, A. Nadeem, and S. A. Memon, “Ranking PCMs for
668 building façade applications using multi-criteria decision-making tools combined
669 with energy simulations,” *Energy*, vol. 215, p. 119102, Jan. 2021, doi:
670 10.1016/j.energy.2020.119102.
- 671 [36] A. Shekhovtsov and W. Salabun, “A comparative case study of the VIKOR and
672 TOPSIS rankings similarity,” in *Procedia Computer Science*, Jan. 2020, vol. 176,
673 pp. 3730–3740, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2020.09.014.
- 674 [37] H. Amoozad Mahdiraji, S. Arzaghi, G. Stauskis, and E. K. Zavadskas, “A Hybrid
675 Fuzzy BWM-COPRAS Method for Analyzing Key Factors of Sustainable
676 Architecture,” *Sustainability*, vol. 10, no. 5, 2018, doi: 10.3390/su10051626.
- 677 [38] P. Chatterjee, V. M. Athawale, and S. Chakraborty, “Materials selection using
678 complex proportional assessment and evaluation of mixed data methods,” *Mater.
679 Des.*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 851–860, Feb. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2010.07.010.
- 680 [39] M. H. Shojaeefard, A. Khalkhali, and E. Miandoabchi, “Multi-criteria decision
681 making approach for selecting the best friction distribution in superplastic
682 forming of a vehicle component,” *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part E J. Process
683 Mech. Eng.*, vol. 230, no. 2, pp. 146–157, Jul. 2014, doi:
684 10.1177/0954408914542858.
- 685 [40] D. K. Dhir, “Thermo-mechanical performance of automotive disc brakes,” *Mater.
686 Today Proc.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1864–1871, 2018, doi:
687 10.1016/j.matpr.2017.11.287.
- 688 [41] M. Saffari, A. de Gracia, S. Ushak, and L. F. Cabeza, “Passive cooling of
689 buildings with phase change materials using whole-building energy simulation
690 tools: A review,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 80. Elsevier
691 Ltd, pp. 1239–1255, Dec. 01, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.139.
- 692 [42] R. P. Singh, H. Xu, S. C. Kaushik, D. Rakshit, and A. Romagnoli, “Charging
693 performance evaluation of finned conical thermal storage system encapsulated
694 with nano-enhanced phase change material,” *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, vol. 151, pp.

- 695 176–190, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2019.01.072.
- 696 [43] N. R. Jankowski and F. P. McCluskey, “A review of phase change materials for
697 vehicle component thermal buffering,” *Applied Energy*, vol. 113. Elsevier Ltd,
698 pp. 1525–1561, Jan. 01, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.08.026.
- 699 [44] M. Kenisarin and K. Mahkamov, “Solar energy storage using phase change
700 materials,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 11, no. 9.
701 Pergamon, pp. 1913–1965, Dec. 01, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2006.05.005.
- 702 [45] M. Rastogi, A. Chauhan, R. Vaish, and A. Kishan, “Selection and performance
703 assessment of Phase Change Materials for heating , ventilation and air-
704 conditioning applications,” *ENERGY Convers. Manag.*, vol. 89, pp. 260–269,
705 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2014.09.077.
- 706 [46] J. Papathanasiou and N. Ploskas, “VIKOR,” in *Multiple Criteria Decision Aid :
707 Methods, Examples and Python Implementations*, Cham: Springer International
708 Publishing, 2018, pp. 31–55.
- 709 [47] A. Jahan and K. L. Edwards, *Multi-criteria Decision Analysis*, 2nd ed. Oxford:
710 Elsevier Ltd, 2015.
- 711 [48] J. F. Nicolalde, J. Yaselga, and J. Martínez-Gómez, “Selection of a Sustainable
712 Structural Beam Material for Rural Housing in Latin América by Multicriteria
713 Decision Methods Means,” *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 12, no. 3, 2022, doi:
714 10.3390/app12031393.
- 715 [49] S. Opricovic and G. H. Tzeng, “Compromise solution by MCDM methods: A
716 comparative analysis of VIKOR and TOPSIS,” *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 156, no.
717 2, pp. 445–455, Jul. 2004, doi: 10.1016/S0377-2217(03)00020-1.
- 718 [50] S. H. Mousavi-Nasab and A. Sotoudeh-Anvari, “A new multi-criteria decision
719 making approach for sustainable material selection problem: A critical study on
720 rank reversal problem,” *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 182, pp. 466–484, 2018, doi:
721 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.02.062.
- 722 [51] J. H. Zar, “Significance testing of the spearman rank correlation coefficient,” *J.
723 Am. Stat. Assoc.*, vol. 67, no. 339, pp. 578–580, 1972, doi:
724 10.1080/01621459.1972.10481251.
- 725 [52] L. Granta-Design, “CES-Edupack.” Granta Design Limited, Cambridge, 2019.
- 726 [53] V. N. Burlayenko, H. Altenbach, T. Sadowski, S. D. Dimitrova, and A. Bhaskar,
727 “Modelling functionally graded materials in heat transfer and thermal stress
728 analysis by means of graded finite elements,” *Appl. Math. Model.*, vol. 45, pp.
729 422–438, May 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.APM.2017.01.005.
- 730 [54] Dassault Systems, “Thermal analysis,” *Solidworks Help*, 2012.
731 [https://help.solidworks.com/2012/english/SolidWorks/cworks/IDH_Analysis_Ba
732 ckground_What_is_Thermal_Analysis.htm?id=74ee73343767426c9ee76a679444
733 c1a3#Pg0](https://help.solidworks.com/2012/english/SolidWorks/cworks/IDH_Analysis_Background_What_is_Thermal_Analysis.htm?id=74ee73343767426c9ee76a679444c1a3#Pg0) (accessed Mar. 06, 2021).
- 734 [55] I. Glodová, T. Lipták, and J. Bocko, “Usage of Finite Element Method for
735 Motion and Thermal Analysis of a Specific Object in SolidWorks Environment,”
736 *Procedia Eng.*, vol. 96, pp. 131–135, Jan. 2014, doi:
737 10.1016/J.PROENG.2014.12.131.

- 738 [56] I. R. Dadour, I. Almanjahie, N. D. Fowkes, G. Keady, and K. Vijayan,
739 “Temperature variations in a parked vehicle,” *Forensic Sci. Int.*, vol. 207, no. 1–
740 3, pp. 205–211, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.forsciint.2010.10.009.
- 741 [57] Y. Cengel and M. A. Boles, *Termodinámica*, 8th ed. McGraw-Hill
742 Interamericana, 2015.
- 743 [58] M. Keshavarz-Ghorabae, “Assessment of distribution center locations using a
744 multi-expert subjective–objective decision-making approach,” *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 11,
745 no. 1, p. 19461, 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-98698-y.
- 746 [59] X. Cheng, X. Xu, and X. Liang, “Homogenization of temperature field and
747 temperature gradient field,” *Sci. China Ser. E Technol. Sci.*, vol. 52, no. 10, pp.
748 2937–2942, 2009, doi: 10.1007/s11431-009-0244-8.
- 749 [60] A. C. Evers, “DEVELOPMENT OF A QUANTITATIVE MEASURE OF THE
750 FUNCTIONALITY OF FRAME WALLS ENHANCED WITH PHASE
751 CHANGE MATERIALS USING A DYNAMIC WALL SIMULATOR,”
752 University of Kansas, 1989.
- 753

Table Appendix

Table 1. List of Phase Change Materials and their thermo-physical properties

Compound (M)		Phase change Temp (°C)	Density (kg/m ³)	Heat of fusion (kJ/kg)	Specific heat capacity (kJ/kg K)	Thermal conductivity (W/m K)
RUBITHERM GmbH, PCM SP 24 E	M1	24	1500	190	2	0.6
RUBITHERM GmbH, PCM SP 26 E	M2	25	1500	190	2	0.6
RUBITHERM GmbH, PCM SP 25 E2	M3	24	1500	180	2	0.6
Micronal PCM 26 Gibsbauplatte, BASF	M4	25	770	385	1.6	0.20
PlusICE PCM, (Salt Hydrate) S25	M5	25	1530	180	2.2	0.54
PlusICE PCM, (Salt Hydrate) S23	M6	23	1530	175	2.2	0.54
savENRG PCM-HS24P	M7	24	1820	185	2.26	1.09
savENRG PCM-HS22P	M8	23	1820	185	3.05	1.09
RUBITHERM GmbH, PCM PX 27	M9	25	650	102	1.6	0.2
PlusICE PCM, (organic) A25H	M10	25	810	226	2.15	0.18
RUBITHERM GmbH, PCM RT 27	M11	25	880	179	2	0.2
PlusICE PCM, (organic) A25	M12	25	785	150	2.26	0.18
PlusICE PCM, (organic) A23	M13	23	785	145	2.22	0.18
PlusICE PCM, (organic) A24	M14	24	790	145	2.22	0.18
Octadecane	M15	28	774	243	2.3	0.15
Calcium chloride hexahydrate (CaCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O)	M16	27.45	1496	161.15	2.2	0.53
Polyglycol 600	M17	23	1100	127.2	2.26	0.16
EPS - E23	M18	23	1475	155	0.69	0.43
EPS - E28	M19	28	769	193	2.22	0.21
TEAP Energy - TH 24	M20	24	1710	175	2	1

[45];[43];[44]; [60]

Table 2. Boundary conditions for charge

Element	Parameter
Roof Initial Temperature	12°C
Roof Final Temperature	45°C
Temperature Time Lapse	5 hours
PCM Initial Temperature	12°C
Internal Air Initial Temperature	12°C
Environmental Temperature	24°C
Convection coefficient	12 W/m ² K

Table 3. Boundary conditions for discharge

Element	Parameter
Roof Initial Temperature	45°C
Roof Final Temperature	12°C
Temperature Time Lapse	15 hours
PCM Initial Temperature	40°C
Internal Air Initial Temperature	37°C
Environmental Temperature	24°C
Convection coefficient	12 W/m ² K

Table 4. Meshing

Study name	20 mm PCM Models
Mesher Used	Blended curvature-based mesh
Jacobian points for High quality mesh	4 points
Max Element Size	22.0025 mm
Min Element Size	14.6682 mm
Mesh quality	High
Total nodes	113712
Total elements	70751
Maximum Aspect Ratio	17.853
Percentage of elements with Aspect Ratio < 3	89
Percentage of elements with Aspect Ratio > 10	1.02
% of distorted elements (Jacobian)	0
Number of distorted elements	0
Convergence tolerance	0.1 %

Table 5. Weighted criteria

	Phase change Temp (°C)	Density (kg/m ³)	Heat of fusion (kJ/kg)	Specific heat capacity (kJ/kg K)	Thermal conductivity (W/m K)
	Deviation ($S'_{ij} - S_i$)				
	0.005	0.024	0.078	0.137	0.183
	0.010	0.023	0.077	0.136	0.182
	0.005	0.024	0.071	0.138	0.184
	0.010	0.108	0.172	0.105	0.035
	0.010	0.021	0.071	0.151	0.168
	0.000	0.022	0.068	0.153	0.171
	0.005	0	0.070	0.145	0.255
	0	0	0.068	0.179	0.247
	0.012	0.153	0.000	0.123	0.041
	0.010	0.107	0.105	0.153	0.023
	0.011	0.099	0.076	0.148	0.038
	0.011	0.116	0.052	0.168	0.024
	0.000	0.118	0.048	0.168	0.024
	0.006	0.117	0.048	0.167	0.024
	0.025	0.111	0.113	0.160	0.000
	0.022	0.024	0.057	0.151	0.166
	0	0.075	0.032	0.186	0.009
	0	0.032	0.065	0.000	0.172
	0.024	0.111	0.081	0.154	0.042
	0.005	0.007	0.065	0.132	0.249
Removal Effect	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5
	0.170	1.291	1.416	2.858	2.236
Weight	0.02	0.16	0.18	0.36	0.28

Table 6. VIKOR Ranking

Compound	Phase change Temp (°C)	Density (kg/m ³)	Heat of fusion (kJ/kg)	Specific heat capacity (kJ/kg K)	Thermal conductivity (W/m K)	S_i	R_i	Q_i	Rank
M1	0.02	0.12	0.12	0.16	0.15	0.56	0.16	0.25	5
M2	0.01	0.12	0.12	0.16	0.15	0.56	0.16	0.25	4
M3	0.02	0.12	0.13	0.16	0.15	0.57	0.16	0.26	7
M4	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.22	0.27	0.52	0.27	0.46	10
M5	0.01	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.16	0.56	0.16	0.26	6
M6	0.02	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.16	0.57	0.16	0.27	9
M7	0.02	0.16	0.13	0.12	0.00	0.42	0.16	0.12	2
M8	0.02	0.16	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.16	0.01	1
M9	0.01	0.00	0.18	0.22	0.27	0.68	0.27	0.62	19
M10	0.01	0.02	0.10	0.14	0.27	0.54	0.27	0.50	13
M11	0.01	0.03	0.13	0.16	0.27	0.60	0.27	0.54	16
M12	0.01	0.02	0.15	0.12	0.27	0.57	0.27	0.53	14
M13	0.02	0.02	0.15	0.13	0.27	0.59	0.27	0.55	17
M14	0.02	0.02	0.15	0.13	0.27	0.58	0.27	0.54	15
M15	0.00	0.02	0.09	0.11	0.28	0.50	0.28	0.48	12
M16	0.00	0.12	0.14	0.13	0.17	0.56	0.17	0.26	8
M17	0.02	0.06	0.16	0.12	0.28	0.64	0.28	0.61	18
M18	0.02	0.11	0.14	0.36	0.20	0.84	0.36	1.00	20
M19	0.00	0.02	0.12	0.13	0.26	0.53	0.26	0.46	11
M20	0.02	0.15	0.13	0.16	0.03	0.48	0.16	0.17	3

Table 7. TOPSIS Ranking

Compound	Phase change Temp (°C)	Density (kg/m ³)	Heat of fusion (kJ/kg)	Specific heat capacity (kJ/kg K)	Thermal conductivity (W/m K)	D_j^+	D_j^-	C_j	Rank
M1	0.005	0.043	0.039	0.076	0.070	0.08	0.07	0.47	5
M2	0.005	0.043	0.039	0.076	0.070	0.08	0.07	0.47	4
M3	0.005	0.043	0.037	0.076	0.070	0.08	0.07	0.47	6
M4	0.005	0.022	0.080	0.061	0.023	0.12	0.07	0.39	10
M5	0.005	0.044	0.037	0.083	0.063	0.09	0.08	0.46	7
M6	0.004	0.044	0.036	0.083	0.063	0.09	0.07	0.46	8
M7	0.005	0.052	0.038	0.086	0.126	0.06	0.13	0.67	2
M8	0.004	0.052	0.038	0.116	0.126	0.05	0.14	0.73	1
M9	0.005	0.019	0.021	0.061	0.023	0.13	0.05	0.27	19
M10	0.005	0.023	0.047	0.081	0.021	0.12	0.07	0.37	13
M11	0.005	0.025	0.037	0.076	0.023	0.12	0.06	0.33	18
M12	0.005	0.022	0.031	0.086	0.021	0.12	0.07	0.36	14
M13	0.004	0.022	0.030	0.084	0.021	0.12	0.07	0.35	15
M14	0.005	0.023	0.030	0.084	0.021	0.12	0.07	0.35	16
M15	0.005	0.022	0.050	0.087	0.017	0.12	0.07	0.39	11
M16	0.005	0.043	0.033	0.083	0.061	0.09	0.07	0.45	9
M17	0.004	0.031	0.026	0.086	0.019	0.12	0.06	0.34	17
M18	0.004	0.042	0.032	0.026	0.050	0.13	0.04	0.22	20
M19	0.005	0.022	0.040	0.084	0.024	0.11	0.07	0.37	12
M20	0.005	0.049	0.036	0.076	0.116	0.07	0.11	0.62	3
V ⁺	0.005	0.019	0.080	0.116	0.126				
V ⁻	0.004	0.052	0.021	0.026	0.017				

Table 8. COPRAS weighted matrix

Compound	Phase change Temp (°C)	Density (kg/m ³)	Heat of fusion (kJ/kg)	Specific heat capacity (kJ/kg K)	Thermal conductivity (W/m K)	S_{+i}	S_{-i}	Q_i	U_i	Rank
M1	0.0010	0.0101	0.0092	0.0173	0.0190	0.047	0.010	0.052	69%	5
M2	0.0011	0.0101	0.0092	0.0173	0.0190	0.047	0.010	0.052	69%	4
M3	0.0010	0.0101	0.0087	0.0173	0.0190	0.046	0.010	0.052	69%	6
M4	0.0011	0.0052	0.0186	0.0138	0.0063	0.040	0.005	0.051	68%	9
M5	0.0011	0.0103	0.0087	0.0190	0.0171	0.046	0.010	0.052	68%	7
M6	0.0010	0.0103	0.0085	0.0190	0.0171	0.046	0.010	0.051	68%	8
M7	0.0010	0.0123	0.0090	0.0196	0.0345	0.064	0.012	0.069	91%	2
M8	0.0010	0.0123	0.0090	0.0264	0.0345	0.071	0.012	0.076	100%	1
M9	0.0011	0.0044	0.0049	0.0138	0.0063	0.026	0.004	0.039	52%	19
M10	0.0011	0.0055	0.0109	0.0186	0.0057	0.036	0.005	0.047	62%	13
M11	0.0011	0.0059	0.0087	0.0173	0.0063	0.033	0.006	0.043	57%	17
M12	0.0011	0.0053	0.0073	0.0196	0.0057	0.034	0.005	0.045	59%	14
M13	0.0010	0.0053	0.0070	0.0192	0.0057	0.033	0.005	0.044	58%	15
M14	0.0010	0.0053	0.0070	0.0192	0.0057	0.033	0.005	0.044	58%	16
M15	0.0012	0.0052	0.0118	0.0199	0.0047	0.038	0.005	0.049	64%	11
M16	0.0012	0.0101	0.0078	0.0190	0.0168	0.045	0.010	0.051	67%	10
M17	0.0010	0.0074	0.0062	0.0196	0.0051	0.032	0.007	0.040	52%	18
M18	0.0010	0.0100	0.0075	0.0060	0.0136	0.028	0.010	0.034	45%	20
M19	0.0012	0.0052	0.0093	0.0192	0.0066	0.036	0.005	0.048	63%	12
M20	0.0010	0.0115	0.0085	0.0173	0.0317	0.058	0.012	0.063	84%	3

Table 9. Spearman's correlation

Correlation of 20 materials ranked			
	COPRAS	TOPSIS	VIKOR
COPRAS	-	0.997	0.988
TOPSIS	-	-	0.988

Table 10. Selected material for simulation

Compound	Phase change Temp (°C)	Density (kg/m³)	Heat of fusion (kJ/kg)	Specific heat capacity (kJ/kg K)	Thermal conductivity (W/m K)
savENRG PCM- HS22P	23	1540	185	3,05	0,54

Table 11. Temperature comparison

Time Lapse	Maximum T°				Internal air T°			
	0mm PCM	5mm PCM	10mm PCM	20mm PCM	0mm PCM	5mm PCM	10mm PCM	20mm PCM
3.600 s	18,1	19,3	20,2	19,9	17,4	17,7	17,8	17,5
7.400 s	24,8	24,8	24,8	24,8	24	23,8	23,4	22,3
10.800 s	31,6	31,6	31,6	31,6	30,7	29,8	28,9	26,9
14.400 s	38,3	38,4	38,4	38,4	37,5	35,9	34,4	31,6
18.000 s	45,1	45,3	45,2	45,1	44,2	41,9	40	36,3